

Research paper

Is scaling plasma technology for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances removal from leachate worthwhile: Life cycle assessment perspective

Dobril Valchev^{a,*}, Irina Ribarova^a, Elisa Blumenthal^b, Massimiliano Sgroi^b

^a Department of Water supply, Sewerage, Water and Wastewater Treatment, University of Architecture, Civil engineering and Geodesy, 1046, 1 Hristo Smirnenski Blvd., Sofia, Bulgaria

^b Department of Science and Engineering of Materials, Marche Polytechnic University, 60131, 12 Via Breccie Bianche, Ancona, Italy

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ABSTRACT

Landfill leachate is a primary source of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) contamination in the environment. Non-thermal plasma (NTP) treatment has demonstrated promising results in terms of PFAS destruction; however, challenges related to scalability, cost, and environmental impact assessment persist. This study conducts a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate the environmental performance of NTP-based technology and its potential for scaling up, based on published laboratory-scale data. Furthermore, a comparison has been made between NTP technology and traditional evaporation and incineration for PFAS removal. Sofia Landfill's leachate treatment facility in Bulgaria served as a case study. The site's leachate treatment facility currently incorporates conventional mechanical and biological treatment processes, with a reverse osmosis (RO) system being planned as a future final step. Three alternatives were evaluated: 1) A1-RO1/P involves the application of plasma treatment to the RO concentrate; 2) A2-RO2/P includes a second-stage RO system with plasma treatment for its concentrate; and 3) A3-RO2/E comprises of a second-stage RO system with concentrate evaporation and off-site incineration of its sludge. The LCA has identified human toxicity potential, freshwater and marine ecotoxicity, freshwater eutrophication and global warming potential as the five key impact categories. The analysis indicates that Bulgaria's electricity mix was the primary impact contributor, followed by transportation. The plasma-based alternatives demonstrated superior performance over the evaporation-incineration alternative, with A2-RO2/P achieving the lowest normalized environmental impact. However, pilot experiments are needed to validate these conclusions. Moreover, the expansion of LCA databases is imperative to enhance the evaluation of PFAS's environmental implications.

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a collective nomenclature for over 4700 individual compounds, the vast majority of which are synthetic [1]. These chemical compounds are non-aromatic in nature, comprising carbon chains ranging from 4 to 18 atoms, with hydrogen atoms either partially or completely substituted by fluorine. C-F bonds are among the strongest chemical bonds in organic chemistry, contributing to the exceptional stability of PFAS [2]. Due to the properties outlined above, PFAS are utilized extensively in industrial settings. However, they also demonstrate a high degree of environmental persistence. The presence of these elements has been identified on a global scale in various environmental media, including treated drinking water, groundwater, surface water bodies, rainwater, snow, municipal

wastewater, biosolids from WWTPs, landfill leachate and sludge. In addition, these compounds have been detected in biota, found in surface water bodies, and even human urine [3,4]. Currently, no biological or abiotic processes that would result in the complete mineralization of these substances in nature have been identified [2]. A substantial number of scientific studies have demonstrated the high toxicity of various compounds in the PFAS group, both to humans and to the environment [5–8].

The final destination of the PFAS-containing products is the landfill sites. The complexity and persistence of PFAS exceed the containment capabilities of conventional landfilling practices [9]. Recent studies have reported levels of PFAS in landfill leachates ranging from tens to hundreds of thousands of nanograms per liter. For instance, recent large-scale original research and review studies have reported

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: dvalchev_fhe@uacg.bg (D. Valchev).

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concentrations of up to 43.3 µg/L in Chinese landfills [10], up to 172.9 µg/L in the US [11], up to 31.4 µg/L in North America, up to 17.6 µg/L in Europe, and up to 16.8 µg/L in Australia [12]. Annually, U.S. landfills release 460 kg of PFAS via landfill gas and 750 kg via landfill leachate [13]. Furthermore, the same study estimated that 84% of PFAS loading to landfills (7.2 tons total) remains in the waste mass, 5% is emitted via landfill gas and 11% via leachate on an annual basis. The transportation of PFAS to wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), groundwater, and surface waters is a consequence of leachate. In wet climates, elevated levels of PFAS have been shown to enhance mobility, necessitating further investigation [14,15].

The PFAS removal technologies can be categorized into two distinct groups. The first category encompasses technologies employed for the separation and concentration of PFAS. Such treatment systems include adsorption processes like granulated activated carbon (GAC) and natural mineral or biomaterial adsorbents, membrane processes, nanomaterials, and anion exchange resins (AIX). These processes may be employed in isolation or in combination, depending on the specific requirements of the given application [15]. As Lu et al. [16] demonstrate, this group attains high PFAS removal efficiencies (>95% for RO or NF and 70–99% for GAC and/or AIX, depending on the PFAS form) [16]. However, the separation processes only retain PFAS into a high-concentration aqueous stream (reverse osmosis (RO) and nanofiltration (NF) concentrate or AIX regenerate) or contain them in solid-phase waste (exhausted GAC/AIX material), requiring further management [15,17][17]. This poses a number of challenges, necessitating additional treatment for concentrates, recirculation into landfill cells or costly disposal of PFAS-laden solid waste [12,14].

The second category encompasses destruction technologies targeting C-F bond cleavage. This group includes advanced reduction processes (ARP), advanced oxidation processes (AOP), UV/H₂O₂, ozonation, Fenton and photo-Fenton processes, UV/persulfate, plasma, incineration, and pyrolysis [15,18,19]. The second group has the capacity to defluorinate the main flow, concentrated PFAS solutions from RO/NF, AIX concentrate, or evaporated sludge/salts after distillation [16]. However, higher technology readiness level (TRL) destruction methods, such as incineration and pyrolysis, are characterized by their high energy intensity. In contrast, oxidation processes at lower TRLs encounter validation challenges associated with the scaling of costly laboratory and pilot-scale reactors [13,15,19].

Non-thermal plasma (NTP) technology is considered to be among the most promising and effective processes in the second category of treatment methods. This technology functions by generating reactive oxidative species and reductive species at a gas-liquid interface [20]. In thin-water-film NTP reactors, these species have been shown to trigger stepwise defluorination, achieving >90% removal of short- and long-chain PFAS in landfill leachate [19,21]. The process is resistant to interference from co-contaminants such as organic matter. In contrast to the processes of adsorption or filtration, NTP mineralizes PFAS into carbon dioxide and fluoride ions, thereby minimizing waste products [21]. Its capacity for continuous-flow or batch operation, in conjunction with its moderate energy requirements when compared to alternative PFAS removal technologies, serves to enhance its scalability potential [20,21]. Research is currently conducted at a laboratory scale. Following a comprehensive review of the current scientific literature, only three studies were identified as having employed plasma-based treatment of landfill leachate. These were a paper by Singh et al. [19], a report by Tang et al. [22], and an article by Eeso et al. [21] that reached similar conclusions about PFAS treatment efficiencies and energy requirements. The technology has been demonstrated to be effective under controlled conditions, with steps having been taken towards its utilization in real landfill leachate matrices [19]. The challenges associated with NTP technology include the scaling of reactor designs, the management of energy costs, and the assurance of performance across variable leachate compositions, with sufficient data and research to support these endeavors [15]. As the scientific literature on plasma

treatment of landfill leachate has reported the presence of degradation intermediates, their fate requires further in-depth investigation and specific classification in order for the plasma-treated leachate to safely and consistently meet regulatory compliance [19,21].

Despite the potential of NTP for the treatment of PFAS in landfill leachate, no data were identified for its full-scale application. Such data are essential for evaluating the feasibility and costs of the process. Consequently, the timely preliminary evaluation of the technology's potential environmental impacts is crucial before attempts for high-cost scaling of the technology.

This paper aims to address the gap through a preliminary evaluation on NTP's environmental performance using published laboratory-scale data. Among various assessment approaches, including environmental product declarations (EPD), environmental impact quantification (EIQ), carbon footprint measurement (CF), water footprint analysis (WF), environmental impact assessment (EIA), and life cycle assessment (LCA), LCA was selected. It is the most widely used of these methods and is regarded as the "gold standard" by most researchers in the field [23–26]. Furthermore, LCA offers diverse environmental metrics and supports quantitative comparisons between traditional and innovative technologies by evaluating resource use and impacts throughout their entire life cycles [27]. However, no research reports on LCA application for NTP in PFAS removal from landfill leachate were found. Thus, beyond evaluating NTP's environmental performance, this paper also identifies strengths and weaknesses of the LCA approach for assessing PFAS removal and plasma technologies. A comparative analysis of three alternatives was conducted: i) NTP after reverse osmosis (RO); ii) NTP after two ROs to concentrate the flow and iii) conventional evaporation and incineration as a benchmark. Sofia Landfill's leachate treatment facility in Bulgaria served as a case study.

2. Materials and methods

The assessment is conducted in accordance with the ISO 14,040 (2006) and ISO 14,044 (2006) series of standards on LCA in its four phases: (1) Goal and scope definition; (2) Life cycle inventory; (3) Impact assessment (LCIA); and (4) Interpretation. Phases 1 and 4 do not necessitate the utilization of specialised tools and are relatively straightforward to execute, provided that the requirements stipulated in the ISO 14,040 and ISO 14,044 series of standards are adhered to [25, 26].

2.1. LCA goal and scope

2.1.1. The LCA goal

The LCA was conducted on the plasma treatment technology for the reduction of the PFAS concentration in the leachate from the Sofia landfill site in Bulgaria. The objective of this study is twofold: firstly, to assess the relative performance of two alternatives using plasma treatment for PFAS removal, and secondly, to compare them with a technology that has been successfully used for large-scale PFAS destruction. The latter involves evaporation of the main flow and off-site incineration of the remaining sludge/salts.

2.1.2. System definition

The Sofia solid waste management facility possesses a total capacity of 3 234 000 tons, with a daily handling capacity of up to 450 tons of waste in solid aggregate form, including separated fractions from commercial, industrial, and administrative activities. The Sofia landfill facilities treat waste from approximately 24% of the country's population [28].

Fig. 1 presents a satellite image of the Sofia landfill. The solid waste is introduced into the receiving bunker initially. Subsequently, the fractions that are suitable for recycling and Refuse-Derived Fuel (RDF) are separated in the installations of the Sofia solid waste plant, and the remaining waste is then sent to the landfill cell.

Fig. 1. The site of the Sofia solid waste plant and its landfill cells.

Fig. 2. Technological schemes, flows, PFAS concentrations, and system boundaries of the three alternatives.

Two leachate treatment plants (LTPs) are available at the site. LTP1 treats the landfill leachate, while LTP2 treats the leachate from the receiving bunker and mainly condensate generated from the production of RDF. In the present study, the LCA is performed for LTP1. The technology employed for the treatment of leachate follows the conventional method for treating municipal wastewater. The process includes a mechanical stage comprising of sieves and grit chambers, succeeded by a biological treatment phase in sequencing batch reactors (SBRs), lamella clarifiers and rapid sand filters (SF). An installation for reverse osmosis (RO) is currently included in the investment plans of the landfill authorities. The study assumes that the RO unit has been installed.

- System boundaries

Three distinct alternatives were analyzed, as shown in Fig. 2. The first two alternatives incorporate the emerging NTP technology, which has demonstrated promising results in laboratory conditions for treating landfill leachate containing PFAS. To minimize the energy required to destroy PFAS, the liquid should have as little organic content as possible. Reverse osmosis (RO) provides such preliminary treatment, which is why an RO stage is included before the plasma reactors in all alternatives. While alternatives 1 and 2 utilize plasma treatment, alternative 3 (conventional incineration) was included as a benchmark for comparison purposes. Given the uncertainty in estimating PFAS treatment efficiency due to the early developmental stage of the technologies, literature data supports the assumption that all three alternatives are comparable, achieving a minimum PFAS removal efficiency of 90%.

- **Alternative 1 (A1 – RO1/P): Plasma treatment unit (P) for the concentrate from the single stage RO (RO1)**

This alternative involves the implementation of plasma treatment on the concentrate of the single stage RO unit that is presumed to have been installed at the LTP1. The flow rate of the concentrate is lower than that of the landfill leachate flow, however, the concentration is higher, rendering it a more economically viable option than installing the plasma treatment in the main landfill leachate flow.

- **Alternative 2 (A2 – RO2/P): Addition of a second stage RO unit combined with a plasma treatment unit (P) for the second stage RO concentrate (RO2)**

This alternative is an enhancement over Alternative 1. The implementation of an additional, secondary RO unit prior to the plasma reactor is designed to decrease the flow rate and increase the PFAS concentration in comparison to Alternative 1, aiming at more efficient utilization of the subsequent plasma reactor.

- **Alternative 3 (A3 – RO2/E): Addition of a second stage RO unit combined with an evaporation installation (E) for the second stage RO concentrate (RO2), after which the sludge/salts are transported for incineration off-site**

This alternative is analogous to Alternative 2, with the exception that plasma treatment is not included after the second stage RO. Instead, the implementation of an evaporation unit is proposed to facilitate the separation of the liquid from the solid phase. The liquid fraction (distillate) is then returned to the permeate water, while the solid residue (sludge/salts) is transported to an incineration facility off-site. PFAS removal occurs outside the system boundaries in this particular case, since there is no available on-site incineration unit. It should be noted that, in this alternative, the environmental impact of the incineration of the salts is considered negligible, however, there will be impacts arising from transportation.

The system boundaries of these three alternatives are shown in Fig. 2.

- Functional unit

In accordance with LCA ISO series of standards, the functional unit must be selected in a manner that permits a quantified evaluation of the function or service provided by the system under study. The functional unit of the system is selected to be the "cubic meter of system inlet

water [m³"].

2.2. Limitations of the analysis, assumptions and inventory analysis

2.2.1. Defining the limitations of the analysis

The principal limitations of the conducted LCA are attributable to the unavailability of pilot or full-scale plasma treatment facilities for landfill leachate. This is an innovative technology that is still under study at the laboratory scale only. Consequently, parameters such as energy demand, retention time and treatment efficiency must be scaled up by a significant factor, which increases the uncertainty of the results. Thus, the absence of a comprehensive database from laboratory experiments, which would facilitate uncertainty estimation and assessment of result variability is the first limitation of the study.

A further limitation is that the first stage RO unit at the Sofia leachate treatment plant is not installed yet, resulting in a lack of operational data.

A third limitation is the lack of comprehensive data sets for PFAS concentration and electrical conductivity (EC) in the investigated leachate. However, six sampling campaigns were conducted for evaluation of the PFAS concentration at different stages of the LTP1. The mean value of the expected first stage RO inlet PFAS concentration was 1.5 µg/L which was adopted for the assessment in the present study.

2.2.2. Assumptions and inventory (LCI)

Regardless of the aforementioned limitations, it is important to note that the same set of assumptions has been applied to all alternatives, which serves to enhance the reliability of the comparative results.

The following assumptions have been made:

- Assumption set 1: Performance of the first stage RO unit (along the leachate treatment line)

A review of the literature suggests that given the measured EC of the leachate flow, the main RO1 unit (a standard single stage RO with 6 membrane modules per pressure vessel is assumed) retains approximately 30% (70% recovery) of the treated water [29,30] and 98% of the inlet PFAS concentration (98% rejection rate) [31].

- Assumption set 2: Performance of the second stage RO unit (for the treatment of the concentrate from the first stage RO unit)

According to the literature, given the calculated EC of the concentrate from the main RO1 unit, the additional RO2 unit (a standard pressure vessel with 6 membrane modules is accepted) will function with a more concentrated inflow resulting in lower recovery rate. It is assumed that the second stage RO retains approximately 40% (60% recovery) of the treated water [29,32] and 98% of the inlet PFAS concentration (98% rejection rate) [31].

- Assumption set 3: Plasma reactor

The specific technological parameters for the reactor components, power consumption, reagent use, etc. were only documented in Singh et al. [19]. In addition, an earlier study by the same author's team, namely Singh et al. [20], utilised analogous reactor components for the degradation of PFAS from liquid investigation-derived waste, obtained from development and purge monitoring wells at thirteen distinct site investigations of Air Force installations. As the preceding two studies utilised laboratory to pilot-scale reactors and accumulated sufficient data to execute an engineering-based scaling up to a full-scale installation, the plasma reactor in this study for LTP 1 at the Sofia solid waste facility was principally designed on the basis of those two studies [19, 20]. The plasma reactor parameters were scaled according to the technological parameters that had been utilised in both studies. It has been hypothesised that the hydraulic retention time (HRT) will be two hours, a duration sufficient to degrade both long-chain and short-chain PFAS [19].

The depth of the reactor is designed to be 0.1 m with argon aeration and surfactant dosing, in order to achieve adequate contact between the reactive species produced by the plasma and the treated water in this reactor [19,20]. The selection of Ni-Cr rods is predicated on their

capacity to generate high-voltage plasma sparks. The number of the rods discharging plasma over the surface has been calculated based on the area of effect and the depth of the reactor used in the Singh et al. [19] study. Argon gas was selected as the gas carrier due to its proven higher efficiency in plasma reactors in comparison to other gas carriers [19,33, 34]. The argon gas aeration intensity was also selected based on the landfill leachate [19].

It is hypothesised that the introduction of the hydrocarbon-based cationic surfactant cetrimonium bromide (CTAB) into the designed plasma reactor will enhance the transport of short-chain PFAS to the plasma-liquid interface, thereby increasing their removal efficiency and reducing treatment time [19,33–35]. It is estimated that the plasma reactor has achieved a 90% reduction in PFAS, as indicated by the findings reported in Singh et al. [19].

Assumption set 4: Evaporation unit

The energy consumption of the evaporation unit, employed in A3-RO2/E, is estimated as an average value for evaporators with analogous capacity utilized for wastewater treatment [36–39]. The quantity of residual sludge requiring transportation and off-site incineration (subsequent to evaporation) is calculated based on the assumption that 95% of the water is recovered as distillate, as indicated in the data provided by evaporator manufacturers [40]. The PFAS concentration in the distillate and the PFAS emissions after off-site incineration are considered negligible.

Assumption set 5: PFAS emissions, antiscalant manufacturing, and surfactant production

Considering the limitations imposed by the Ecoinvent database with regard to certain required substances for the comprehensive LCA, the present study utilized the following surrogates:

- In an effort to estimate the environmental and human health impacts, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) have been proposed as a substitute for PFAS. This proposal follows the observation reported by Feng et al. [41] that PFAS have similar human health effects to PCBs.
- Phosphoric acid production is defined as "purification of wet-process phosphoric acid to industrial-grade product in 85% solution state". This is a process that compensates for the absence of a generic antiscalant in the database. The basis of the assumption is that the most commonly used antiscalant agents for RO membranes are produced from phosphoric acid [42];

- Non-ionic surfactant production as "non-ionic surfactant production, fatty acid derivate" has been assumed as a CTAB substitute.

The designs of the technological process within each system for the three alternatives are based on the average quantity of the leachate inflow. No hourly, daily, seasonal or annual fluctuations are taken into account due to lack of sufficient reliable data.

In order to calculate the specific material and energy inputs of the plasma reactors with greater precision, engineering drawings of the modelled full-scale reactors were produced using AutoCAD 2025 (Fig. 3).

The three alternatives were analysed exclusively in terms of their operation, consequently, the following categories of inputs are considered in the study:

- Energy - given that the original site is based in Bulgaria, the inputs concerning the energy consumption of each system component are based on the energy mix of Bulgaria;
- Materials – inputs are based on the used materials in the operation of each system;
- Transportation - the delivery inputs are based on the shortest distance to the closest off-site incineration plant.

The output flows that are considered are as follows:

- The emissions to air are generated outside the system boundaries, i.e. at the upstream energy production stage. These are directly calculated using the Umberto® LCA+ v11 software;
- Emissions to water - these include PFAS that are not reduced during the treatment, and nitrates, that are produced into the treated water from the nitrogen in the surrounding air during the plasma treatment process.

The estimated input and output values of the flows are presented in Table 1. Precise calculations and considerations for each of the input and output values are presented in Table S 1 to Table S 4 from the Supplementary material.

2.3. Used software for phase 3 of the LCA

The phase 3 (LCIA) poses a significant challenge due to its reliance on

Fig. 3. Engineering drawings of the plasma reactor of the two alternatives.

Table 1
Inputs and outputs of the three alternatives.

Inputs				
Energy, kWh/m ³ system input				
Type	A1 RO1/P	A2 RO2/P	A3 RO2/E	Reference
Plasma generation				
High voltage (HV) power supply - 40 kV, for the plasma generator	26	18.72	No	[19] and [20]
Low voltage (LV) power supply - 210–230 V, for cooling of the transformer and the capacitors - fans and pumping	3.88	3.14	No	[43–46]
Aeration				
Compressor for recirculation of argon (99.35% of the flow)	1.16	0.33	No	[47]
Reagent dosing				
Mixing of the preparation tank and pumping (vertical mixer and dosing pumps)	4.92	4.08	No	[45,48]
Evaporator^a				
Energy consumption (heating, vacuum, recirculation pumping, cleaning, etc.)	No	No	28	[36,37]
RO unit				
Pumping, backwash, reagent (sulfuric acid and antiscalant) preparation and dosing, etc.	No	6.55	6.55	[49] and [45]
Materials, kg/m³ system input				
Type	A1	A2	A3	Reference
Aeration of plasma reactor				
Gas carrier (Argon) - mass	0.70	0.28	No	[19,50] and [20]
Reagent dosing for plasma				
Reagent Cetrimonium bromide (CTAB) - 0.4mM	0.15	0.06	No	[19]
Water mass for solution preparation	492.85	197.14	No	–
RO unit				
Sulfuric Acid	No	6	6	[30]
Antiscalant	No	0.005	0.005	[51,52]
Delivery, t[*]km/m³ system input				
Type	A1	A2	A3	Reference
Plasma reactor				
Delivery of Argon (approx. 8.5 m ³ =300cf vessels)	1.33	0.54	No	[53]
Delivery of Cetrimonium bromide (CTAB)	0.06	0.02	No	–
Evaporator				
Delivery of the remaining solid phase after evaporation to the closest incineration plant	No	No	18.57	[40]
RO unit^b				
Delivery of Antiscalant**	No	0	0	–
Delivery of Sulfuric acid consumption**	No	0	0	–
Outputs				
Emissions to water ^c , kg/m ³ system input				
Type	A1	A2	A3	Reference
PFAS	0.50 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.49 × 10 ⁻⁶	No	[19]
Nitrates	0.10	0.04	No	[54,55]
RO unit				
PFAS	No	0.60 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.60 × 10 ⁻⁷	–

^a Only evaporation energy is considered, as incineration occurs off-site with negligible energy use for the remaining salts, taking into account the amount of waste that is put into the existing plant as a whole.

^b Due to the low quantities, the materials for the second stage RO will be delivered with the materials for the main RO unit.

^c Evaporation and incineration of PFAS emissions are negligible.

the richness of the available database for the requisite calculations, a process that demands the use of specialised software. In this study, the Swiss Ecoinvent v3.10 database within the Umberto® LCA+ v11 software was used. The Umberto LCA software is developed on the basis of the ReCiPe method version 2016 [56]. The software first calculates the values of 18 midpoint impact categories. The subsequent calculation step involves the normalisation of the obtained values for these 18 midterm impact categories. During the normalization process each category is recalculated so that equal measuring units are applied to all of them to enable their comparison and grouping. A commonly used reference is the average yearly environmental load in a country or continent, divided by the number of inhabitants. In this study the normalization was performed according to the revised normalization scores of ReCiPe 2016 (“Normalization Scores ReCiPe 2016 | [56]).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Impact assessment (LCIA)

The estimation of all 18 midterm impact categories of the ReCiPe2016 methodology has been conducted. The potential impact for each of the eighteen categories was standardized and expressed as people equivalent/m³. The results of the study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Environmental impacts of the three alternatives in the different midterm impact categories given in people equivalent/m³.

Environmental Category (Abbreviation)	Environmental Category (Full name)	A1 RO1/P (Result x10 ³)	A2 RO2/P (Result x10 ³)	A3 RO2/E (Result x10 ³)
EOFP	Photochemical ozone formation potential: ecosystem	1.96	1.75	2.68
FEP	Freshwater eutrophication potential	58.71	53.46	56.73
FETP	Freshwater Eco toxicity potential	57.04	61.80	94.27
FFP	Fossil resources scarcity potential	5.20	4.65	5.88
GWP	Global warming potential	2.49	2.22	2.71
HOFP	Photochemical ozone formation potential: human health	1.65	1.48	2.25
HTPc	Human toxicity potential (cancer)	321.24	291.53	355.64
HTPnc	Human toxicity potential (non-cancer)	1.38	1.34	1.67
IRP	Ionising radiation potential	24.09	21.54	22.30
LOP	Land use related impact (soil quality)	0.15	0.11	0.11
MEP	Marine eutrophication potential	2.17	1.15	0.54
METP	Marine Eco toxicity potential	45.28	49.39	74.93
ODP	Ozone depletion potential	0.11	0.09	0.09
PMFP	Particulate matter formation potential	1.76	2.28	2.53
SOP	Mineral resources scarcity potential	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
TAP	Terrestrial acidification potential	2.31	3.58	3.94
TETP	Terrestrial Eco toxicity	6.00	7.55	15.07
WCP	Water use (scarcity potential)	0.70	0.99	0.97
	Total impact:	53.22	50.49	64.23

Regarding the total scores, the analysis indicates that the three alternatives are comparable, with relatively close results. However, a subsequent ranking of the options reveals that A2-RO2/P is the most favourable option, while A3-RO2/E is the least favourable option.

In order to understand the sources of the environmental impacts, the analysis has been strengthened further for the four categories with the highest impacts (impact score $>50 \times 10^{-3}$) - HTPc, FEP, FETP, and METP, with the addition of GWP, due to its great significance globally (see Table 2). A visual representation of the materials, energy, and transportation flows that contribute to these impacts is provided in Fig. 4.

These results demonstrate that electricity, irrespective of its voltage, constitutes to be the primary contributor to the observed environmental and human impact. The second most notable contributor is transportation, followed by the use of sulphuric acid in the membranes within the RO unit. With the exception of the FEP, A3-RO2/E exhibits the highest negative impact across the other four categories. It is observed further that Alternatives 1 (RO1/P) and 2 (RO2/P) demonstrate closely comparable performance with higher potential impact for A1-RO1/P in GWP, HTPc and FEP, and for A2-RO2/P – in FETP and METP.

Another important aspect of the analysis pertains to the manner in which each stage of the respective alternative contributes to the studied impact. In this regard, the normalized results for the three alternatives are compared in terms of the technological stages within each system. Taking into consideration the significance of the global warming potential as the most commonly used parameter for impact assessment nowadays, an additional analysis for the technological processes has been conducted for GWP specifically. The results are presented graphically in Fig. 5.

The graphs indicate that the evaporator has the highest potential impact, followed by the plasma generation (with greater contribution in A1-RO1/P) and the operation of the RO unit. As for the GWP, Alternative 3 (RO2/E) has the highest potential, largely due to the extensive energy consumption of the evaporation unit.

3.2. Interpretation

In accordance with the ISO 14,040 and 14,044:2006 standards, the interpretation of an LCA should encompass the following components: 1) The identification of significant issues is to be based on the results of the LCI phase. 2) The study itself is to be evaluated, including an assessment of its comprehensiveness, sensitivity and consistency. 3) The conclusions, limitations and recommendations are to be provided subsequently.

3.2.1. Identification of significant issues based on the results of the LCI phase

3.2.1.1. Energy considerations. Despite that the energy generation occurs outside of the systems' boundaries (an upstream process), the environmental impact of the energy consumption is the primary contributor to the total impact of all alternatives, given the energy-intensive nature of plasma, RO and evaporation technologies. It is evident that alternative flows, such as materials and transportation, exert a significantly lower impact in comparison to that of energy utilization. The present study's findings are consequently dependant on the Bulgaria's national energy mix, which is presented in Fig. 6.

According to the latest report of the National Statistical Institute of Bulgaria [57], the largest proportion of the energy mix in Bulgaria consists of relatively equal parts thermal and nuclear gross power production (approximately 40% each). As outlined in Section 3.1, four of the primary impact categories of the studied LCA alternatives are GWP, HTPc, FETP, and METP. It is widely acknowledged that these elements are closely associated with the emissions released into the air and aquatic environments, which are attributable to industrial activities or

power plants that utilize incineration processes. These emissions encompass a range of pollutants, including CO₂, SO₂, NO₂, particulate matter (PM 10 and PM 2.5), and metals such as Ni, Cu, Co, and Zn, which are released as a result of the burning practices or mining activities [56, 58–61].

3.2.1.2. PFAS impact assessment and ecoinvent database limitations. Given that all studied alternatives have the objective of degrading PFAS (which are present in very low concentrations) and reducing their toxic effects on the environment, the PFAS impact is negligible when compared to all other contributors. In addition to the energy assessment, it is imperative to comprehend the impact of plasma technology on PFAS emissions, given the specific objective of the study. A more profound understanding of the environmental and human health implications of PFAS is needed, as the current knowledge in this area is limited. The expansion of LCA databases is necessary to enhance the assessments of the impact of PFAS. This point is especially important given the data from the OECD [62], which reports that as of 2018, there were 4 730 PFAS registered with a CAS number. A recent analysis reveals that 20 of these substances have been included in the EU Directive 2020/2184, and in the national legislation of certain countries, such as the USA and Germany [63–65]. Furthermore, the advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) employed for water treatment, of which plasma treatment is a constituent, generate by-products with the potential to exert even greater toxicological effects on the environment [66–68]. However, laboratory studies have demonstrated the efficiency of plasma treatment in the degradation of shorter-chained PFAS, including Gen X and ADONA, among others. The potential for further reduction of the impact of PFAS is anticipated with the development of a more comprehensive database [19,20,69].

3.2.2. Evaluation of the study itself, including an assessment of its comprehensiveness, sensitivity and consistency

3.2.2.1. Evaluation of the scope. The study evaluates all input flows, including energy, materials, and transportation, during the operational phase of the systems. It should be noted that the production of reactors, plasma sources, membranes, cables, and related components has not been included in the scope of the study. The exclusion of these components may result in discrepancies in the impact category results, particularly due to the frequent replacement of membranes in A2-RO2/P and A3-RO2/E.

3.2.2.2. Environmental impact - comparison of the alternatives. With regard to the environmental impact, the plasma treatment alternatives (1-RO1/P and 2-RO2/P) demonstrate superior environmental performance in comparison to the evaporation and off-site incineration alternative (3-RO2/E). As demonstrated in Fig. 5, A2-RO2/P exhibits the lowest environmental impact, with an assigned score of 0.5049. This is followed by A1-RO1/P (score of 0.5322) and A3-RO2/E (score of 0.6423). The latter is the most energy-intensive and consequently has the highest environmental impact. The supplementary second stage of the RO process has been shown to reduce the volume of the plasma-treated liquid, while simultaneously increasing the concentration of PFAS in the water medium. This, in turn, results in a decrease in the energy demand and an increase in the efficiency of the plasma reactor, leading to the superior performance of A2-RO2/P compared to A1-RO1/P.

However, it should be noted that LCA produces results based on mid-term indicators, which aggregate individual pollutants and material flows. Subsequent normalization highlights the most significant values, which may, in turn, lead to the overlooking of certain important aspects. In the case of plasma technology, nitrates are generated and although they are considered in the LCA as an output flow, their importance remains somewhat obscured due to the very low normalized value within the relevant mid-term impact category. For selection of a treatment

Fig. 4. Materials, energy, and transportation flows contributing to the top five highest potential impacts.

Fig. 5. Normalized impact and GWP per technological stage for each alternative.

Fig. 6. Gross energy production in Bulgaria (NSI 2023).

technology for engineering projects, it is necessary to identify additional measures to reduce nitrate concentrations to environmental standards for discharge into surface water bodies. In this paper, the recirculation of the final effluent for irrigation of the landfill body is presented as a potential solution (see Fig. 2).

3.2.2.3. *Potential for further optimization and need for experimental validation.* It is recommended that further research into methods for reducing the flow and increasing the PFAS concentration prior to the plasma treatment is conducted, as this could enhance its efficiency. One promising approach is the recirculation of the concentrate through the RO membranes on multiple occasions, as opposed to the utilization of an additional module for a second stage of RO [49]. Nevertheless, it was not possible to evaluate such a scenario using the current available data, due to the lack of sufficient information regarding the fluctuations of the flow and the concentrations of the specific contaminants, especially PFAS, which is the main subject of the study. In this regard, to enhance

the credibility of the study itself, it is essential that further analyses are conducted in order to verify the assumptions and the data sets through the execution of additional experiments.

4. Conclusions

The objective of this study was to conduct a preliminary assessment of the environmental performance of plasma treatment for PFAS removal from landfill leachate, comparing it with processes that have already been applied on a larger scale for PFAS destruction – namely, evaporation and incineration. Three distinct alternatives for LCA analysis designed for the LTP1 at the Sofia solid waste plant, Bulgaria, were evaluated: 1) A1-RO1/P involves the application of plasma treatment to the RO concentrate; 2) A2-RO2/P includes a second-stage RO system with plasma treatment for its concentrate; and 3) A3-RO2/E comprises of a second-stage RO system with concentrate evaporation and off-site incineration of its sludge.

The results from the LCA demonstrate that the four categories with the highest impacts are as follows: HTPc, FEP, FETP and METP. Further analysis has been conducted for GWP due to its considerable significance. With regard to the environmental impact contributors, electricity, irrespective of its voltage, is the primary agent leading to the observed environmental and human impact. This phenomenon is primarily attributable to the upstream impacts of Bulgaria’s electricity mix, which predominantly comprises of equal shares (approx. 40% each) of thermal and nuclear gross power production. The second most significant contributor is transportation, followed by the utilization of sulphuric acid in the membranes within the reverse osmosis unit. Apart from the FEP, A3-RO2/E exhibits the highest negative impact across the remaining four categories. It is further observed that Alternatives 1 (RO1/P) and 2 (RO2/P) demonstrate closely comparable performance, with higher potential impact for A1-RO1/P in GWP, HTPc and FEP, and for A2-RO2/P - in FETP and METP.

With regard to the normalized results, the plasma treatment alternatives (1-RO1/P and 2-RO2/P) demonstrate superior environmental performance in comparison to the evaporation and off-site incineration alternative (3-RO2/E). It is evident from the overall normalized scores that A2-RO2/P exhibits the lowest environmental impact, with a score of 0.5049. This is followed by A1-RO1/P (score of 0.5322) and A3-RO2/E (score of 0.6423).

However, limitations in the LCA database, which currently cannot assess PFAS environmental impacts, prevented thorough consideration of this critical factor in our study. Additionally, the environmental risks of potential intermediates or by-products formed during plasma treatment require further research. Therefore, alongside validating the reported results through pilot studies, expanding the LCA database to evaluate PFAS impacts is essential.

The findings indicate that further exploration into plasma technologies is worthwhile. Further analysis is required in order to gain a more robust understanding of two key areas. Firstly, the optimal concentration and flow prior to plasma reactors must be determined. Secondly, the most economically, technically and environmentally feasible technologies for the pre-treatment for concentrating the flows must be identified.

This study was limited to comparing alternatives for their environmental performance using LCA approach. Before deciding to implement any of the considered alternatives, their overall performance, including nitrates generation, cost-efficiency, operational challenges, and advantages, should also be evaluated.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dobril Valchev: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Irina Ribarova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Elisa Blumenthal:** Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Massimiliano Sgroi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Dobril Valchev reports financial support was provided by H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. Irina Ribarova reports financial support was provided by H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. Elisa Blumenthal reports financial support was provided by H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. Massimiliano Sgroi reports financial support was provided by H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials. Dobril Valchev reports a relationship with H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials that includes: funding grants. Irina Ribarova reports a relationship with H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials that includes: funding grants. Elisa Blumenthal reports a relationship with H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials that includes: funding grants. Massimiliano Sgroi reports a relationship with H2020-EU.3.5. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials that includes: funding grants. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106081](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106081).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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